

How ClassPoint Affects Learners in an English Class

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Abstract:- ClassPoint is an interactive tool that is embedded with Power Point presentations. In the light of using ICT in the classroom, the researcher made an action research to find out how the app helped 111 Grade 10 students of Don Leon Mercado Sr. Memorial National High School, San Juan, Btangas, Philippines. The researcher used survey questionnaire and employed a qualitative-descriptive approach. The results of the survey shows that ClassPoint has high acceptance rate among the students in terms of making the lesson fun, easy and interactive as well as making them excited, competitive and engaged during the lesson.

I. CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

The use of ICT in the classroom has shown significant impact to the motivation and engagement of students in both the online and in-person setup. It is found out in the study of Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015) that teaching and learning with technology is more effective than the traditional classroom setup with board and chalk. Using ICT tools and equipment ensure an active learning environment that is more interesting and effective for both teachers and students that is why its use is always anticipated. Some of the most common technologies used in the Don Leon Mercado Sr. Memorial National High School are Kahoot, mentimeter, Quizziz and even tutorial videos prepared by teachers.

The researcher used ClassPoint in teaching Grade 10 English. It is an interactive tool that can be embedded in Microsoft PowerPoint which allows the users to turn existing slides into an interactional presentation. With ClassPoint, the delivery of quiz questions can be done without using another application during the session. It has several mode of questions, including multiple-choice questions, short questions, quick poll, word cloud, short answer, slide drawing and image upload. In addition, ClassPoint has features that make teachers annotate the presentation as the teacher presents the lesson. Students only need their phones to join the collaborative activities by just logging into <http://classpoint.app>, then enter the class code and create a username that would be used throughout the lesson.

II. PROPOSED INNOVATION, INTERVENTION AND STRATEGY

A. Idea

In the absence of learning management system in Don Leon Mercado Sr. Memorial National High School, one of the most commonly used media in teaching is MS Powerpoint. It is often used by teachers in because the application is already available on computers or on laptops and teachers do not have to master the development of new information technology-based media and do not have to be studied more deeply. Although MS Powerpoint is helpful as a tool for learning, students feel bored at the same time and find it hard

to concentrate since DLMSMNHS only have 36” televisions in the classrooms. Thus, the researcher thought of using ClassPoint app in the presentations.

Integrating ClassPoint tool activities into the EFL classrooms significantly improves the students’ e-learning satisfaction as compared to the non-ClassPoint-integrated learning mode (Abdelrady, 2022).

III. ACTION RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How do the students perceive the use of ClassPoint in making the class/lesson
 - a. Fun
 - b. Easy
 - c. Interactive
2. How do the students perceive the use of ClassPoint in making them
 - a. Excited
 - b. Competitive
 - c. Engaged

IV. ACTION RESEARCH METHODS

A. Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

Participants of the study are 111 Grade 10- Einstein, Farday and Euclid students of Don Leon Mercado Sr. Memorial National High School for the SY 2022-2023. The data will be based from their answers in the survey questionnaire.

B. Data Gathering Methods

Survey will be utilized about the students’ perception on the use of ClassPoint in the English 10 class. The researcher also used unstructured interviews to get the students’ reaction about ClassPoint.

➤ Procedures for data collection

The researcher will ask permission from the school principal as well as the parents of select Grade 10 students who will serve as respondents of the study. Further, the data will be collected after the introduction of ClassPoint for interpretation, analysis and recommendation of an intervention program about the use of ClassPoint as a permanent tool for classroom interaction in English.

C. Data Analysis Plan

➤ How the data will be analyzed and reported

The data will be analyzed through simple analysis and interpretation of the gathered answers from the survey. Results will be the basis of designing an intervention plan. Results will be presented to select Grade 10 students, their

parents and the school principal who would be partners in the employment of a crafted plan from the study.

➤ *Qualitative and/or quantitative methods used in analyzing the data*

This study utilized qualitative-descriptive method.

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND REFLECTION

This section contains the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the study’s major findings. It reveals the results relative to the perceptions of the Grade 10 students in using ClassPoint and the action plan for the proposed intervention.

The students answered the survey regarding their experience in using ClassPoint and the scale between 1 to 5 was used to interpret the answers. The scale has the following interpretation:

- 1- Strongly disagree
- 2- Disagree
- 3- Neutral
- 4- Agree
- 5- Strongly agree

A. This section will discuss how the students describe learning while using ClassPoint.

Fun means commitment while doing and learning the activities. It is noted that when students are engaged and having fun, they turn on their effective information processing and long-term memory storage and the information is retained.

Table 1.1

Table 1.1 presents how the students’ perceive ClassPoint in making learning fun. 50% of the students agreed that the app make learning fun while 35.34% of the respondents strongly believe ClassPoint’s ability to make learning enjoyable. In the three sections, only 10-Faraday

learners had more students who strongly agreed as compared to those who agree that ClassPoint makes learning fun.

Table 1.2

According to Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, easy means not difficult can be done or obtained without a lot of effort or problems. Based on the survey conducted, 49.14% of the respondents believed that ClassPoint makes learning easy. It was followed by 33.62% of students who believe that the inclusion of ClassPoint either makes learning easy.

The third hypothesis is that ClassPoint will make learning interactive. The word “interactive” is about having all participants, in this research the students participating enthusiastically in the activities. When we talk about interactive in learning, it is considered as a a method whereby the learner is viewed as a participant expected to perform certain actions such as listener, observer but more importantly takes active part in what is going on (Suvorova, 2001).

Table 1.3

Table 1.3 shows the result of the students’ perception on ClassPoint as an interactive tool. Majority of the students (43.97%) believe that it makes learning collaborative. It can also be noted that there is only a slight difference (3.45%)

between the students who strongly agreed and are neutral about it.

B. This part discusses the students’ personal experience as they use ClassPoint. The effect of the application to the students’ encounter will be a factor whether the innovation will be continued or not.

Table 2.1

Being excited means being very enthusiastic and eager. Based on the table, 54.31% of the students agreed that ClassPoint make the students excited about their learning. 29.31% of the students thought that they strongly agree that ClassPoint makes them enjoyable.

Collins dictionary defined competitive as people or firms compete with one another. Based on the table, 56.03% of the respondents said that they become driven in answering questions since ClassPoint has a feature to see who is in the leader board. On the other hand, those who are neutral (21.55%) exceeded the number of those who agree (17.24%) that ClassPoint makes them aggressive.

Table 2.2

The third component studied is the ability of ClassPoint to make the students busy, occupied and involved in the class activities. 54.31% of students agreed that they are engrossed with the lessons while using ClassPoint.

Table 2.3

Although students had encountered difficulty in using ClassPoint such as the absence of signal inside the classroom and load to connect, the students are still positive on the use of ClassPoint in the class. 61.21% agreed that ClassPoint should be at least once a week while 21.55% strongly agreed.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of survey, the following conclusions were derived:

- ClassPoint makes learning fun, easy and interactive.
- Further, it makes the students excited, competitive, and engaged in their lessons.
- Students also want to use ClassPoint in their English class.

RECOMMENDATION

With the drawn conclusions from the study, the following recommendations were made

1. ClassPoint must be used in the English classes at least once a week.
2. Internet access for students in all areas of the school must be ensured so that students and teachers would not need to avail load wallet to connect to the internet via data.

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